

A Facile [Hydroxy(tosyloxy)iodo]benzene Mediated Synthesis of Substituted Imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridines[†]

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Synthesis of 2-substituted imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridines (3a-f) has been accomplished by a one-pot procedure involving reaction of 2-aminopyridine with a variety of ketones in presence of [hydroxy(tosyloxy)iodo]benzene. The process results in the exclusive formation of the single isomer 3. Some of the compounds have shown significant antifungal activity.

Hypervalent iodine(III) reagents have recently generated a considerable interest for the synthesis of a wide variety of heterocyclic compounds¹⁻⁴. In continuation of our efforts in developing convenient I(III) mediated methods for the synthesis of various type of compounds associated with wide range of physiological activities⁵⁻⁷, we undertook the synthesis of 2-substituted imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridines through a simple methodology.

Three types of methods are available for the synthesis of such type of ring systems. First method involves condensation of alpha-halogenoketones with 2-aminopyridines^{8a}. In another approach hydroxyethylaminopyridines obtained by treating 2-chloropyridine with ethanolamine^{8b} were cyclized thermally⁹ or by using SOCl₂^{8b}, whereas the third method commences with an imidazole derivative, followed by construction of the pyridine ring^{8c}.

Results and Discussion

It is well established that synthesis of alphasoyloxyketones can easily be achieved by treating a variety of ketones with [hydroxy(tosyloxy)iodo]benzene (HTIB)³. These compounds are stable, crystalline solid and provide a safe eco-friendly alternative route to the synthesis of compounds conventionally prepared through alpha-halogeno-ketones, which are not only lachrymatory and toxic but are unstable and difficult to purify.

We report in this paper a one-pot HTIB-mediated synthesis of imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridines using several aromatic ketones and 2-aminopyridine in excellent yield following a simple work up (Procedure A, Scheme 1). In principle, the reaction of alpha-tosyloxyketones could lead to the formation of 2- or 3-substituted imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridines via intermediates of type 3' and 4' respectively. However, the reaction invariably provided substituted imidazo[1,2-*a*]pyridine (3) which was found to be same as obtained by an unambiguous synthesis reported by Schmid and Bangler^{10a} by treating 2-aminopyridine with dypnone [PhCOCH=C(Me)Ph]. Thus, there is considerable evidence

that the ring nitrogen of aminopyridine is the site of electrophilic attack by alpha-tosyloxyketones. Intermediacy of alpha-tosyloxyketones (2) in this reaction was also demonstrated by the conversion of acetylketones into the corresponding tosyloxy derivatives which on treatment with 2-aminopyridine yielded 3 (Procedure B, Scheme 1). Procedure A was found to be more convenient than Procedure B.

In view of the biological significance of this ring system several compounds were evaluated for their antibacterial and antifungal properties. Although no noticeable antibacterial activity was observed, a few compounds (3a and 3e) displayed interesting level of antifungal activity (Table 1).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. ¹H nmr spectrum was recorded on a Bruker 300 MHz FT NMR spectrometer and mass spectrum on a Kratos MS-50 spectrometer. Elemental analysis was carried out on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 instrument.

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

TABLE 1—ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUNDS **3a** AND **3e**

Concn. ppm	% Inhibition over control		
	<i>A.alternata</i>	<i>R.bataticola</i>	<i>C.lunata</i>
Compound 3a :			
1	19.60	2.00	16.90
10	20.48	10.30	22.50
20	23.49	11.40	26.70
50	34.03	15.30	36.60
100	44.57	21.52	56.31
1000	83.13	59.64	84.51
Compound 3e :			
1	20.00	1.10	6.70
10	22.68	3.00	15.90
20	27.23	4.13	28.60
50	31.00	4.23	35.80
100	36.00	5.90	37.84
1000	70.00	57.38	74.90

Imidazo[1,2-a]pyridines. Procedure B (via isolation of alpha-tosyloxyketone) (2a) :

Alpha-tosyloxy-para-nitroacetophenone. Step-I : To a stirred solution of *p*-nitroacetophenone (1, 1.79 g, 0.01 mol) in acetonitrile was added HTIB (3.9 g, 0.01 mmol) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for ~2 h. Excess of acetonitrile was then distilled off and the residual mass was crystallized from ethanol. The product was further washed with cold ethanol and dried (70%, 2.67 g), m.p. 136–37° (lit.^{10b} 138°).

2-(4-Nitrophenyl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine. Step-II : To a solution of 2-aminopyridine (0.6 g, 6 mmol) in ethanol was added a pinch of sodium bicarbonate. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h. An equimolar amount of **2a** was subsequently added and the mixture was refluxed for ~6 h. The solvent was then filtered and on cooling a crystalline product was obtained which was filtered, washed and recrystallized (62%, 1.11 g), m.p. 263° (lit.¹¹ 264°).

One-pot synthesis of 3 starting from acetyl compounds. Procedure A :

Imidazo[1,2-a]pyridines : To a solution of the ketones (**1a-f**) in acetonitrile was added equimolar amount of HTIB and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h. Excess acetonitrile was then distilled off. The formation of the respective alpha-tosyloxyketones was confirmed by tlc monitoring of the reaction mixture. To an ethanolic solution of the 2-aminopyridine taken separately, was added a pinch of sodium hydrogen carbonate. The mixture was refluxed for ~4 h. It was added to the alpha-tosyloxyketone in acetonitrile and the reaction mixture was further refluxed for 4 h. The solvent was then distilled off under reduced pressure and cooled to provide the products as crystalline solids which

were filtered, washed with saturated bicarbonate solution and crystallized from aqueous ethanol : *2-(4-nitrophenyl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine (3a; 72%),* m.p. 263° (lit.¹¹ 264°); *2-(phenyl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine (3b; 70%),* 133° (lit.¹² 135°); *2-(4-fluorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine (3c; 76%),* 163° (lit.¹³ 165°); *2-(4-chlorophenyl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine (3d; 68%),* 208° (lit.¹⁴ 208°); *2-(4-methoxyphenyl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine (3e; 66%),* 139° (lit.¹⁵ 139–40°); *2-(4-methylphenyl)imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine (3f; 67%),* m.p. 137° (Found : C, 80.80; H, 5.81; N, 13.46. Calcd. for : C, 80.80; H, 5.80; N, 13.45%), ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 2.39 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.73–6.78 (1H, m, imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine-6H), 7.60–7.63 (1H, d, imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine-7H), 7.82 (1H, s, imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine-3H), 7.84–7.86 (2H, m, ArH), 7.12–7.16 (1H, m, imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine-5H), 7.18–7.26 (2H, m, ArH), 8.09–8.12 (1H, m, imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine-4H), HRMS *m/z* M⁺ 208.10004 (C₁₄H₁₂N₂ requires : *m/z* M⁺ 208.2628).

Antibacterial screening : All the compounds were screened for antibacterial activity by the zone inhibition method. The following strains of bacteria were tested : S-386/97 – *Salmonella senftenberg*, S-388/97 – *Salmonella senftenberg*, S-437/97 – *Salmonella enteritidis*, S-438/97 – *Salmonella enteritidis*, S-476/97 – *Salmonella typhi* and S-477/97 – *Salmonella typhi*.

None of the compounds was found active against the above bacterial strains.

Antifungal screening : The antifungal activity was tested by following poisoned food technique¹⁶. The potato dextrose aqueous medium was prepared and sterilized. To this medium was added fungal toxicant and different concentrations were prepared. The culture of following parasitic fungus were prepared : *Alternaria alternata*, *Curvalaria lunata* and *Rhizoctonia bataticola*.

A culture of test fungus was grown on PDA for a certain period (7 days). Small disc (7 cm) of fungus was cut and transferred aseptically in the centre of the petridish containing the medium, with a certain amount of fungicide. Fungus colony diameter was measured every 24 h.

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